

THE ROLE OF SHORT STORIES IN DEVELOPING STUDENTS' LANGUAGE SKILLS

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<https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7867740>

ARTICLE INFO

Received: 18th April 2023

Accepted: 25th April 2023

Online: 26th April 2023

KEY WORDS

Short story, communicative competence, students, learner-centered, language proficiency, literary genre, critical thinking, linguistic awareness

ABSTRACT

Given the significance of ongoing innovation and advancement in language teaching techniques and the benefits of employing short stories in language classes, a novel language teaching approach disguised as a short story is presented here. The goal of using a short tale as a language teaching tool is to increase students' understanding of their own identities, as well as their cultures and languages. The major goal of short story is to assist students in developing their language abilities by allowing them to appreciate and use language for conversation while using short tales as the teaching materials in a welcoming environment. It improves the pupils' critical thinking and communicating skills.

Literary works aren't usually written with education in mind. As opposed to that, they discuss "things which mattered to the author when he wrote them" [5, 12]. Therefore, the language is far richer and more diversified than the language samples in the textbooks. There are numerous real characteristics of written language, including "the formation and function of sentences, the variety of possible structures, and the different ways of connecting ideas are presented at many levels of difficulty" [3, 5].

According to Widdowson [6], "by assigning learners to explore the literary language, they have at the same level been encouraged to think about the norms of the language use."

Learners are urged to become familiar with various language forms, uses, and conventions. Such exposure is important for students' language development in particular. Thus, utilizing literature to teach languages has the benefit of introducing students to the target language's culture.

The ability to perceive communication in various social and cultural target language situations is strengthened by short stories [6].

Reading literary works helps students see the world from a different perspective, observing human values and a different way of life while also learning that people around them live in quite different societies. They will comprehend and develop a broader understanding of the social, political, historical, and cultural developments taking place in a particular society. Finally, literature "encourages personal growth and intellectual

development because it enables students to understand and appreciate other cultures, societies, and ideologies different from their own." [2, 2-4].

All language courses are removed from the context of the events and circumstances that give rise to natural language, especially those outside the community of native speakers. This issue can be solved by literature because language in literary works establishes its own environment. The reader's current circumstances become irrelevant as they focus on the events that language has fabricated. These occurrences in turn give the book's language a context of situation and allow it to transcend the contrived classroom setting. Based on these concepts, it is clear that literary works, even if they are fiction, unquestionably help students grasp the language better by giving them real-world experiences and relationships with the culture and individuals who speak the target language. The short tale, as it is defined by Poe "as a narrative that can be read at one sitting of from one-half hour to two hours, and that is limited to "a specific unique or singular impression," to which every detail is subordinate," stands out among literary forms. In addition, a short story tells of one incident in a very concentrated way in relation to this criteria [1, 158]. Additionally, it appears that short stories are the best to employ in secondary schools. Regarding the notion that, due to its conciseness, the short story is the most suited literary genre to use in English teaching.

Four benefits of adopting short stories for language teachers were stated by Smith [7, 3]. "First, short stories are useful because they may be completely read in one or two class periods.

Second, pupils may easily work with short stories on their own because they are not difficult.

Third, there are numerous options for short stories to suit various preferences and interests.

Finally, short stories can be used in morning, afternoon, or evening lessons and with students of all ages, levels, and classes (beginning to advanced).

Short stories can be employed from the primary and intermediate levels for language development, reading comprehension, and aesthetic enjoyment. Short stories introduce literary aspects (theme, message, characters, setting, plot, metaphorical language, culture, and values) and help pupils improve their motivation or sense of interest. Short stories help students develop higher-order thinking skills because they teach them about culture, the past, present, and people's customs and traditions. Short stories also teach students that thinking critically comes more naturally to them and that it can even be enjoyable.

Despite the advantages that short stories provide for students, there are always those who object to their use.

Firstly, understanding short story's complex and figurative language takes a lot of time.

Secondly, it will be challenging to stage a play in a crowded classroom during a short period of time due to the length of a novel.

Short stories could expect pupils to respond personally without adequately preparing them for the story's linguistic complexities.

Some short stories can be too far removed from the students' actual lives for them to be able to react to them in a meaningful way.

On the other hand, some student groups could detest having to talk about their personal emotions or experiences.

This method could be quite mechanical and demotivating if the study of the short tale is conducted solely in language terms with little room for human interpretation.

In language training, the contribution of short stories to language proficiency is crucial. The significance of short stories in language instruction is discussed below. Reading is a complicated interaction between the reader and the text that is influenced by the reader's past knowledge, experiences, attitude, and language community, which is located within a particular cultural and social context. Reading is a skill that needs constant development, practice, and improvement. On the other hand, reading calls for critical thought and inventiveness. The words that readers have read are incorporated into their pre-existing knowledge structure, or schema (schemata theory). Therefore, reading is the process of recognizing writing and signals by looking at them. Reading is allegedly considered an elite skill because it requires special training.

When someone is hearing, listening is a conscious action or something that piques their interest. The following are other requirements for listening: hearing the noises, familiarity with the subject, intonation and stress, ability to deal with repetition and noise, capacity to repeat what is said next, comprehension of colloquial terminology, comprehension of various accents, weariness, and prediction. Students are more likely to come and gain fully from the listening experience if they are listening to something enjoyable. Speaking and listening skills can be taught through short stories in an effective and inspiring way. For improving speaking and listening skills in EFL classes, effective learning activities that center on a short narrative include oral reading, dramatization, improvisation, role playing, and discussion.

Speaking involves mouthing words, using tone and natural expression, interjecting, and expressing oneself through gestures and facial emotions. So speaking refers to the ability to use a sound system to communicate. Additionally, students are exposed to real content, which in the context of this research is language that does not make allowances for non-native speakers. It is regular, everyday speech used by native or proficient language users. If students interact with speakers of the target language in real life, they will experience this, and because it is realistic, it is not likely to be sped up or spoken slowly.

Graphemes are representations of sounds in writing. Before writing, people reflect. Then, writing entails putting ideas in the proper sequence, adhering to grammar rules, knowing the alphabet, and using a variety of language, punctuation, precise spelling, and sentence structure. Language skills can be taught via short stories. Writing, speaking, and listening are examples of productive language skills, while reading, listening, and speaking are examples of receptive language skills.

Conclusion. One of the most popular types of narratives used in language instruction is the short story. Of course, the short story's short length is one of its defining features. Limited time and space dimensions are eliminated in the short narrative. It focuses on a specific aspect of the characters' lives and provides quick access to the action. The use of short stories in English language instruction is supported by a number of factors. A handful of the aforementioned traits already provide an idea of the benefits of short stories. According to the results, it can be inferred that employing short stories and exercises to build all four language

skills can help students' language proficiency. Studying short stories offers many advantages for students, including extending their horizons, encouraging them to consider causes rather than effects, exposing them to various lifestyles, and allowing them to make comparisons between their own culture and other cultures.

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